

From Panic to Purchase: Tracing the Changes in Consumer Behavior During the COVID-19 Crisis

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Rani Nayak
Imperial College, Bargarh
Email: raninayak619@gmail.com

Abstract:

Objective:

The primary objective of this study is to investigate and analyze the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on consumer behavior, specifically focusing on stocking and impulse buying. The research aims to trace the shifts in consumer decision-making processes from the onset of the crisis, with the goal of providing a comprehensive understanding of how external shocks influence purchasing patterns.

Methodology:

To achieve the research objective, an online survey questionnaire was employed as the primary data collection tool. The survey was distributed to a sample of 1500 individuals, and the responses of 558 participants were utilized for analysis. The study utilized Exploratory Factor Analysis to establish the construct validity of the key variables, followed by Confirmatory Factor Analysis to assess the unidimensionality, validity, and reliability of the model. Structural equation modeling was then employed to investigate the specific impact of the COVID crisis on consumer stocking and impulse buying behavior.

Findings:

The research findings indicate a significant and discernible impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on consumer behavior. Specifically, there are noticeable shifts in stocking and impulse buying patterns. The study provides empirical evidence to support the contention that external crises, such as a global pandemic, can lead to substantial changes in consumer decision-making processes, with implications for businesses and policymakers.

Implications:

The implications of this research are crucial for businesses, policymakers, and researchers alike. Understanding how the COVID-19 crisis has influenced consumer behavior in terms of stocking and impulse buying provides valuable insights for businesses looking to adapt their strategies. Policymakers can also benefit from this knowledge when crafting interventions to support economic recovery. Additionally, the findings contribute to the broader understanding of consumer behavior during times of crisis, offering a foundation for future research in this domain.

Limitations:

While this study provides valuable insights, it is not without limitations. The sample size of 558 participants may not fully represent the diversity of consumer behavior, and the reliance on self-reported data introduces the potential for response bias. Additionally, the research is contextualized within the unique circumstances of the COVID-19 pandemic, limiting generalizability to other crisis situations. Finally, external factors not accounted for in the study may also influence consumer behavior during the pandemic, introducing an element of complexity and potential confounding variables.